

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING THE SUBJECT OF THE FORMATION OF MATHEMATICAL REPRESENTATIONS

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Annotation: this article provides a methodology for organizing various activities for the formation of mathematical representations in children of preschool age, as well as modern use for each type of activity.

Keywords: educator-educator, preschool education, mathematics, education - upbringing, mathematical imagination, method, methodology, knowledge, activity, thinking, understanding, game, teaching process, result.

The field of pre-school education, being the first link of the continuous education system, plays an important role in the further education system, in preparing the child for school. Today, it is no coincidence that this field of education has risen to the level of state policy. In this regard, it is known to everyone that a number of decrees, decisions and orders adopted by our state are aimed at the fundamental reform of the preschool education system. PQ-4312 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 8, 2019 "Concept of developing the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", December 29, 2016 "Measures to further improve the preschool education system in 2017-2021 Decree No. PQ-2707, dated September 30, 2017, No. PF-5198, dated September 9, 2017, "On measures to fundamentally improve the management of the preschool education system." Decision No. PQ-3261 on measures to fundamentally improve the education system, as well as No. 1 of the Ministry of Preschool Education dated June 18, 2018, "State requirements for the development of children of primary and preschool age" and State documents, such as the implementation of the State Curriculum of "Ilk Kadam" pre-school educational institution, provide for solving issues related to this field. President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev deeply analyzed this system and paid attention to the smallest aspects that have been overlooked so far. Today, it was found that improving the state requirements for the educational programs and educational plans of preschool educational institutions remains an urgent issue. The material and technical base of most preschool educational institutions does not meet the requirements of the time. The rate of enrollment of children in pre-school education remains low. In order to practically eliminate existing

problems, the decision "On measures to further improve the preschool education system in 2017-2021" was adopted.

In order to further develop science in our country, to educate our youth as possessors of deep knowledge, high spirituality and culture, to rapidly continue the work we have started on the formation of a competitive economy and to raise it to a new, modern level, our honorable president Sh. Mirziyoyev announced the year 2020 in our country. It was announced as the "Year of Science, Enlightenment and Digital Economy Development". In addition, our president said in his speeches: "We should carry out large-scale work on the priority development and reform of the specified sectors during 2020. In particular, it is necessary to increase the level of coverage of children of kindergarten age with preschool education to 60% this year...", and gave several tasks and suggestions in order to further increase the responsibility of personnel working in the field of preschool education. passed.

The main place in the methodology of teaching mathematics to children of preschool age is occupied by questions that are asked as methodical methods. They can be reproductive-mnemonic, reproductive-cognitive, productive-cognitive. The questions should be clear and concise. In the teaching process, there should be a unity of reproductive and productive questions depending on the age of the children and the material to be studied. Questions ensure the development of children's thinking.

Questions for children can often be used to gain control of the group. The most frequently used questions are the so-called closed questions. They have only one correct answer and are used to test knowledge. Open-ended questions during discussions are important to stimulate group activity and analyze the issues at hand.

Let's look at the open questions.

Hypothetical questions. If ..., what would you do, what would you think? They help children to imagine one or another situation, strengthen the thinking process.

Thought provoking questions. How can we help solve this problem?

Stimulating, supporting questions. That's interesting, what happened next? They allow children to share their personal experiences and views.

Feedback questions. What do you think about ...?" Such questions are used to let children know that their opinions are important and interesting.

Probing questions. Why do you think so? This question, asked calmly, helps them to think more deeply about their thoughts and analyze their explanations.

Explanatory, summarizing questions. Am I right if I say that you think...? Summarizing what the child has said and checking that they have understood it correctly encourages others to think about how they might react to the idea.

Consent questions. Do you agree that most ...? Such questions can be asked to encourage discussion. Or at the end of the discussion, Are we done with this part? such questions are asked to get permission to move on to the next topic.

Try to remember not to use ambiguous questions, such as "X is right, isn't it? Such questions reduce the child's activity. Don't ask too many questions at once and don't use ambiguous questions.

- Children should not be forced to defend themselves with questions, they should have the opportunity to choose and create this opportunity themselves. They can be:

- - reproductive-mnemonic (for example: What is this? What color is the flag? What is the name of this figure?);

- - reproductive-cognition (for example: If I put one more cube in the box, how many cubes will be there? Which number is bigger (smaller): 9 or 7?);

- - productive knowledge (for example: What should be done so that the bowls are equal? How do we solve this task? How can we determine what the red flag is according to the calculation?).

Do not ask too many questions at once and do not use ambiguous questions. Questions activate reception, memory, thinking, speech in children. In the formation of elementary mathematical concepts, more complex questions are used, starting from the simple ones, aimed at clarifying the specific signs, properties, results of practical actions of objects, connections, relationships, connections, their explanation and justification, and the use of simple proofs.

More often such questions are asked by the teacher after the example is shown or after the child completes the task. For example, when children divide a paper rectangle into two equal parts, they are asked: "What did you do? What is this part called? Why can each of these two parts be called a half? What is the shape of the part? How to prove that a square is formed? What must be done to divide a rectangle into four equal parts?"

As a methodological method, we highlight some of the main requirements for teacher questions: correctness, accuracy, logical sequence, variety of wording, optimal ratio of reproductive and productive questions of the studied material in accordance with the age of the children, questions of the child to awaken and develop thinking, encourage to think, analyze, compare, contrast, generalize, the number of questions should not be too large, but sufficient to achieve the set

didactic goal, to tell the answer slowly and similar the need to avoid questions, the need to skillfully use additional questions. Questions should be considered as an effective means of activating cognitive activity in the development of children's elementary mathematical imagination and allowing them to think about the answer. Children should be taught to formulate questions independently. With the use of didactic material in a specific situation, the educator offers them to ask questions about the number, size, shape, and measurement methods of objects. We will show the methodological requirements for children's answers:

- short or full questions depending on the nature of the question;
- independent and aware; correct, precise, grammatically correct.
- When creating tasks in the form of using the variant of basic words and phrases, it is necessary to pay attention to the amount of tasks that can be solved using interactive methods. The use of these methods develops children's ability to think, ensures that the material is mastered at a high intellectual level.
- Based on the subject of training, the educator should choose the appropriate of these methods. When using interactive methods in training, it is recommended to follow the following methodological recommendations:
 - preparing a place for work, creating physically comfortable conditions for children, preparing materials for creative work in advance;
 - taking the process and regulations seriously, respecting children's freedom of speech;
 - to pay serious attention to the division of children into groups, to involve all of them in work, to support their mental preparation, to practice in this regard, to constantly encourage their active participation in work, to create an opportunity for the child to express himself;
 - when using interactive methods, to ensure that the number of children in the group is not large, the composition consists of 4-6 people, to work effectively in small groups, to listen to everyone, to allow each group to come up with a statement of the problem. Interactive methods provide for constant interaction between the teacher and the child. Improper use of these methods can lead to a reduction in the effectiveness of these methods or a false understanding of them. In pedagogy, the system of children's questions and answers is called conversation. The conversation method involves a conversation between the teacher and the children with the help of well-thought-out questions, which leads to their independent thinking and acquisition of new concepts. It uses the methods of asking questions, discussing children's answers and comments,

forming conclusions, and correcting answers.

During the interview, the teacher pays special attention to the children's correct use of mathematical terms and speech literacy. This is done with various explanations and their acceptance is clarified. For example, if the teacher teaches children to examine geometric figures, he explains that take the figure in your left hand and show the sides of the square (for example: a right triangle, a triangle). Or another example, if the teacher teaches children to measure, he puts the scale, then shows and tells how to calculate the measurement.

As the children grow up, the problematic questions and situations they are asked also become bigger. The emergence of a problematic situation: the connection between the evidence and the result does not open suddenly, but gradually. This begs the question: What is it? (for example, we drop different objects into water: one sinks, the other does not sink); after describing some parts of the material, the child must guess (for example, melting ice, experimenting with hot water, solving a problem); the use of words such as "sometimes", "some", "only in some cases" serve as specific signs of knowledge; in order to understand an argument, it is necessary to compare it with other arguments, to create a discussion system, that is, to perform some mental operations (for example, to make different measurements, to calculate with a group).

In the problem task method, it is possible to achieve results with the help of problem tasks based on the specific situation and the nature of the problem. It is useful to create a problem situation in the mastering of materials, assignments, and solving exercises and problems. In this case, small groups are formed, educational materials are given to groups separately. After the final conclusions and solutions are found, the topics are exchanged among the groups.

Any pedagogical technology applied to the educational process, regardless of whether its components are passed through the content of the training, the curriculum, the textbook or the activities of the pedagogue, is required to be aimed at the development of the child's free and creative activity. will be done. Teaching methods are the main part of the educational process, without which pedagogical activities cannot be carried out. Depending on the nature of knowledge transfer and reception, it is divided into verbal, demonstrative and practical methods. Explanatory-illustrative, reproductive, problem statement, private search or heuristic and semi-research methods are used to master the content of the training topics.

Practical methods include setting a task (goal), planning a method of its

execution, managing the execution process, analyzing, determining the cause of deficiencies, making corrections and changes to the training process in order to fully achieve the goal. When performing practical exercises, children actively observe their future actions, talk to themselves and interpret the future event.

The method of free thinking is devoted to illustrative pictures, photographs, and their discussions. The purpose of this activity is to expand children's range of knowledge and worldview, by introducing them to pictures, photos, and books, to increase their knowledge and interest, and to apply previously acquired knowledge, skills, and abilities in new situations. to acquire new knowledge.

The assignment should be as follows: it should not be large in size, but it should be meaningful, aimed at mastering, learning, repeating, thinking, and its practical aspect; to be simple and understandable compared to what is done in a group; depending on children's observations and opinions, especially when creating problems, examples and sentences, conducting practical work; that specific instructions have been given for the correct completion of homework; it is necessary to individualize taking into account the readiness and capabilities of children: the educator must check homework on time to ensure children's discipline and responsibility.

In conclusion, it should be said that attention is being paid to the education system in our country at the level of state policy. Mathematical activity of pupils was developed in various conditions: in theatrical activities, in building-making games, in activity centers. Knowing the strengths of children is not only important for the analysis, but also allows to determine prospects for their future career choice, mathematical ability and motivation. Taking into account the child's demonstrated ability is necessary not only for their development, but also for directing his talent to the appropriate stream. Experiences have shown that games and interactive methods help children develop their mathematical abilities, create conditions for wide-ranging math goals and the accumulation of mathematical impressions. requirements" creates the basis for successfully solving tasks.

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